

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE TRANS-CASPIAN INTERNATIONAL TRANSPORT ROUTE THROUGH THE CASPIAN REGION

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Abstract

The Trans-Caspian International Transport Route is one of the branches of the Belt & Road Initiative. Its importance is growing for political reasons: the war in Ukraine and the pressure from the US to limit Chinese business activity in Europe. If trade links between China and the EU are nevertheless maintained, a TITR with a fulcrum in Azerbaijan could absorb much of the now bottleneck traffic on the northern section of the BRI. Bulgaria will be able to take advantage of this through its infrastructure assets if the EU clarifies its strategy on the BRI and revives the TRACECA programme.

Keywords: Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, political factors, infrastructure

Introduction

The Belt and Road Initiative was included in the 13th Five Year Plan in 2015. The BRI represents a strategic effort to create new external markets and preserve old ones. China is willing to open its domestic markets more widely to foreign goods in exchange for greater access for its own export to foreign markets. This change in foreign economic policy has highlighted the main areas of transport flows and the problems that require specific solutions. One of the BRI's branches runs through Central Asia and the Caspian Sea region. Having several options is an insurance against force majeure. The insurance is justified - the Russia-Western Europe trade route is already being restricted since February 2022 and the conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan continues with low intensity.

There are also tensions between the US and China, leading to economic war, involving also the EU. The goal of Chinese diplomacy is to thwart this option. So far Chinese investment in Europe have shown large fluctuations. There is suspicion towards Chinese investments. The total volume of USD 47 billion invested there between 2005 and 2019 is very small for the capabilities of Chinese investors. To prevent China from buying European strategic assets, the EU operates the Committee on Foreign Investment (CFIEU). The BRI's biggest success in Europe so far is from 2019, when Italy joined. So the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank will finance the 'Chinese' projects in the ports of Genoa, Trieste and Palermo, totaling EUR 20-30 billion. Elsewhere, Chinese entry into infrastructure is more cautious.[1]

Fig.1: China investment in the EU and UK

Source: Rhodium group

In Central and Eastern Europe, BRI cooperation is taking place in the "16+1" format (11 CEE countries, 5 Balkan countries and China). So far the initial set of proposed projects is limited. Some of the obstacles are of political nature: the USA used various tools to block Chinese business activity in the Balkans, including

EU trade in goods with China, 2011-2021

Fig.2: EU-China trade dynamics

Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=China-EU_-_international_trade_in_goods_statistics

In 2017, around 40 overland freight routes connected China with Europe. Today the number has almost doubled to 78 lines, reaching 180 cities in 23 European countries.[3] The value of goods transported is growing, from \$8 billion in 2016 to \$74.9 billion in 2021, more than 10% of total volume. While in the beginning the Chinese government offered subsidies up to \$5,000 per container (40 ft)[4], the subsidy for 2023 will no more be needed. (During pandemic, freight per container according reached \$10,000, falling to \$4,000 by the end of September 2022.[5]) However, commodity trade is more susceptible to sudden conjunctural swings. Under pessimistic scenarios, Chinese investment in countries such as Italy, Greece, Serbia and Hungary may be limited to infrastructure projects serving commodity trade, which may also suffer a sharp decline in the coming years.

1. Impact of political factors

The war in Ukraine is already limiting the trade along the Russia-Western Europe route. The restrictions imposed by the EU also affect the transit of Chinese goods through Russia via the New Eurasian Land Bridge. Poland, for example, is refusing to serve as link between China and Europe. The future behaviour of Germany, a major recipient of Chinese cargo via Poland, is also unclear. High tensions with the US which will affect transport in the South China Sea, and there could be a general slowdown in the whole BRI project and a revision of some of its long-term objectives. Transit through Russian and especially Ukrainian territory will not be possible for some time.

Moreover, there is competition between the Russian (EASIS) and Chinese integration projects in the Eurasian space. The common economic and political inter-

NATO expansion in the region, targeted propaganda [2], and pressure on EU institutions.

In contrast to investment, trade in goods between China and the EU, which is more flexible, is growing steadily and doubling between 2011 and 2021.

ests presuppose "coordination" of the two Eurasian integration initiatives. Building Greater Eurasia in this way forces restructuring of global value chains to the benefit of both countries. The partnership allows China to diversify its energy supplies and transport corridors, and the Chinese province of Inner Mongolia has benefited most from this so far. This convergence of interests also extends to security matters: China and Russia "will have Central Asia and Mongolia at their disposal, eliminating the possibility of infiltration of external forces into the heart of Eurasia".[6]

For now, China's Belt and Road project is more attractive, as it offers significant investment and attractive prospects, while Russia is preoccupied with solving security problems on its western border. This opens up opportunities for countries willing to serve as intermediaries in EU-China trade. Probably the BRI logistics chain will operate at reduced capacity in the medium term and the main burden on the land section will shift to the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TITR) - via Kazakhstan, the Caspian Sea, Azerbaijan, Georgia and Turkey to Europe. It is the shortest (6,500 km) route, with a delivery time of two weeks instead of 60 days by sea. Its potential is estimated at 10 million metric tons or 200,000 containers per year[7], half the capacity of the New Eurasian Continental Bridge.

The Caspian region could become a major logistics hub along and opens up opportunities for Bulgaria as a transit link to Central Europe. The land transit could give the small countries along the route a strong impetus for development, and the confrontation between the US and China will make maritime transport riskier and expensive.

Fig.3: Map of TITR

Source: <https://www.railfreight.com/beltandroad/2022/04/07/middle-corridor-utlc-to-be-established-in-2023/>

The pessimistic scenario assumes limiting trade between the EU and China, but even then the TITR could remain busy - a branch of it could head to North- and East African countries. Besides, the North-South transport corridor, linking Russia with India, passes through the Caspian region. In both scenarios, the role of the Caspian region as logistic hub will grow.

2. Geographical and infrastructural features

Many of the caravans of the historic Silk Road used the route through Azerbaijan. Silk, industrial products, spices, pearls, gold and silver have been transported along flourishing Central Asian cities. But the development of shipping gradually reduced the importance of this route and turned Central Asia into an "economic black hole". Now the progress of rail transport and the financial reserves in China enabled the Great Silk Road to regain its historical importance. Azerbaijan, in particular, sees an opportunity through its geographical position to become a major trade and transport hub. The country supports the Silk Road in its new edition and especially its combination with the North-South transport corridor. The 849-kilometre Baku-Tbilisi-Kars rail link already enables unimodal freight transport from Central Asia and Russia to Europe, with a line capacity of approximately 5 million tonnes of goods [8]. Maritime transport infrastructure is also developing rapidly. Ships of the state-owned ASCO connect the ports of Aktau, Kurik (both in Kazakhstan) and Turkmenbashi (Turkmenistan). Shipments have been planned between the ports of Constanta (Romania) and Batumi/Poti (Georgia). Plans for the near future envisage the expansion of the new port of Alat, 65 km south of Baku, from 15 million tonnes of cargo, including 100,000 standard container (TEU) capacity at present, to 25 million tonnes, including 500,000 TEU. [8]

Another section of the BRI is running entirely through Iranian territory, where accelerated road and rail upgrades are underway. The trade volume between China and Iran will raise due to the 25-year strategic cooperation agreement signed in March of that year. The modern road built from Azerbaijan to Iran could reduce obstacles to the whole project. It connects to the

Kars-Nakhichevan rail project between Turkey and Azerbaijan, which opens up another option for Chinese cargo to Turkey and on to Europe. The governments of Iran and Azerbaijan signed a Memorandum which foresees a new railway line, highway and accompanying energy infrastructure.

An even shorter route from China to Europe runs through the Zangezur corridor, crossing the territory of Armenia, but this project (only 160 km in total) has not yet been implemented because of the conflict between Azerbaijan and Armenia. The corridor is among the contentious issues between the two countries. Diverting a large part of the cargo to the Caucasus section of the BRI could bring the neighbours' positions closer, especially if the North-South cargo flow increases as expected. If constructed, the railway would follow the old Soviet standard, and if the railway is extended from Nakhichevan to Turkey, a bogie change station would be built at the border - a technical solution that has already been applied on many occasions. Armenia could be given an alternative railway line to Russia via Azerbaijan - the Ijevan-Gazakh road inherited from the USSR era, which requires minimal investment to restore.[9] Opening up all the above-mentioned routes would facilitate shipments from Central Asia to Georgian ports and Turkey via Kars and could raise the issue of capacity absorption.

3. Opportunities for Bulgaria

For Bulgaria, the development provides an opportunity to set in motion the TRACECA programme - a transport corridor from Europe to Central Asia via the Black Sea region. If there is coordination between the EU and China (introduction of a single transport tariff) the long delays for vehicles at border crossings can be overcome. The revival of the TRACECA programme could start with the construction of a large logistics centre on the Bulgarian Black Sea coast: trade, warehousing and logistics services facilitating trade, transport and re-export through the available airports, sea and river ports and roads.

The concept can rely on the following assets:

1. The Varna port complex with two terminals "East" and "West", with a total of 45 ship berths each

and a working capacity of 10 million tonnes of cargo. The ferry complex of the port allows the transport of "post-Soviet" wagons without transshipment, by changing gauges. The terminal can serve the shortest route between Europe and Asia. The other advantage of Varna is the direct railway line to the port of Ruse at the Danube Corridor No. 7.

2. Port of Burgas with 19 shipping berths and a total volume of handled cargo up to 4 million tons. Burgas also maintains a ferry connection with Poti and Novorossiysk. Burgas Airport has the highest number of sunny days in Europe and has the 3rd longest runway (3200 m) on the Balkan Peninsula. Like Varna airport, it has a large unused capacity during the autumn and winter months. If the existing railway Svilengrad - Nova Zagora - Yambol - Karnobat - Burgas is properly repaired, the port area could become the first point of arrival for Chinese cargo via the Marmaray tunnel and vice versa: the last point of departure for cargo leaving the EU towards China and Central Asia. For the time being, this infrastructure is operating at partial capacity. From a technical point of view, even the relatively small capacity of the Bulgarian logistics infrastructure exceeds the capacity of the TITR. It could be used cost-effective without external funding, but the third factor - political will - is missing.

Conclusion

A realignment of the infrastructure of the global economy is currently underway. The BRI project is capable of accelerating this realignment and is in turn dependent on political considerations. The EU continues to lack a clear strategy towards the Chinese large-scale project, is unable to cooperate with Russia, and cannot yet propose a project of its own to stabilise the Black Sea region. In this situation, the Chinese side is pursuing a strategy of cautious progress and is betting on several alternative directions. The optimistic scenario relies on increasing the transit, incl. through Bulgarian territory. The pessimistic scenario assumes a reduction of this transit and blocking of BRI westwards of Azerbaijan. Without using the trade link options to China and other emerging economies in Asia, our country consolidates its peripheral position in the EU.

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